
THE OPPORTUNITIES OF STORYTELLING IN MULTIMEDIA JOURNALISM

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ABSTRACT

The article analyzes the possibilities of storytelling, which is one of the genres of multimedia journalism. The steps before creating storytelling, platforms for creating storytelling, multimedia elements in it were mentioned. Also, good examples of storytelling on Uzbek websites are given as examples.

Keywords: *internet, journalism, multimedia, storytelling, storyboard, video, audio, text, pictures.*

It is human nature to tell stories and inform others about the events in our lives. Whether the story is factual or fictional, it is a characteristic of a person. In journalism, there are many situations where an event is told in advance through newspapers, magazines, TV or radio. In the conditions of modern journalism, its format has acquired a new look. At a time when the flow of information is rapidly changing, and people are required to read information in a selective manner during “the information storm”, modern methods of conveying the details of the event to the audience not only in text, but in interactive ways have emerged. This allowed the journalist to enrich the story with audio, pictures, and video using interesting multimedia possibilities.

From a historical perspective, journalism has always found itself in search of ways to combine multiple media formats as a means to produce compelling stories [1]. Examples of this are storytelling and longreads on websites. Multimedia storytelling is the art of conveying a narrative through multiple forms of media, such as text, audio and video [2]. This approach provides new opportunities for telling stories. For instance, The New York Times story Snow Fall: The Avalanche at Tunnel Creek, published on 20 December 2012, was selected as a case study to explore the narrative techniques employed in multimedia news stories. Consisting of more than 13,800 words, Snow Fall can be considered a piece of long-form digital

journalism. The story is divided into six parts: Tunnel Creek, To the Peak, Descent Begins, Blur of white, Discovery, and Word Spreads. Each part combines text with photographs, videos, audio, and/or graphic animations [3]. This media material can be a vivid example of storytelling.

Russian scientist Voronkina Y.S. said that the ability to tell a story in an interesting way is an important aspect of journalism, it is not only about conveying "dry" information, but also about active reaction in the audience, emotions (interest, sympathy, participation, desire to help, anger, etc.) that it helps to wake up [4]. With the help of stories and fairy tales, the author can tell complex events without losing the interest of the audience. Image, video, audio formats will help him in this.

A multimedia story is some combination of text, still photographs, video clips, audio, graphics and interactivity presented on a Web site in a nonlinear format in which the information in each medium is complementary, not redundant [5]. Multimedia elements in storytelling should not serve as three different forms of the same media product, but as complementing each other. At its simplest, a multimedia story combines different elements that complement each other to make the story more interesting, complete, or engaging.

Storytelling is more than just telling a story, it is a very powerful tool to influence the minds of large audiences, inspire them with the right ideas, and in a certain way, easily control people.

A certain template alone is not enough to create interesting storytelling. For interesting storytelling, it is important to properly connect all the elements of the structure in one place. Each scene and each episode must be logically connected. Before creating storytelling, it is better to pay attention to some aspects:

1. **Develop idea.** The first step in making a digital story is figuring out an idea for the recovery story you'd like to tell [6]. Before creating any storytelling material, you should ask yourself a number of questions. Specifically, will this story engage the audience? How deep do I know this topic? Are there any supporting materials to help me tell my story? (e.g., photos, data, video)

2. **Develop a plan.** Once you have an idea for a story, you can develop a plan to help organize both your thoughts and resources [7]. There are a number of aspects that need to be followed when developing a plan for storytelling. The reason is that you only have 1-2 minutes to keep the audience. The ability of the audience to read the storytelling to the end is closely related to how carefully your material is prepared. It is necessary to determine in advance what aspects of the subject, in what

order, using what methods. Also, defining your audience is one of the most important processes when you are planning. After all, the distribution of material written for the target audience will be wide. For example, you want to tell a story about the unique aspects and traditions of Japan. First, you need to determine for whom this story is written: foreign tourists, foreign students studying in Japan, foreign citizens who want to work in Japan, and other groups.

3. **Storyboard.** Storyboarding refers to a way of planning for all the things that will appear in the digital story, such as music, pictures, words, text, photos, and video. Storyboards help storytellers to picture the entire story from start to finish.

4. **Choose your media.** Each medium has specific strengths, and depending on the skills and knowledge held by your team, you may find yourself leaning on some media more than others. When creating your storyboard, identify which medium can be used for which constituent part of your story [8].

Video. An excellent tool for conveying action and emotion, but limited in its ability to show processes or explain complexity.

Pictures. Great for conveying emotion and the scale of landscapes. In the story, it is necessary to place pictures of people's portraits that reflect their feelings.

Audio. Works well with other media such as photos or videos. Shorter clips have more impact. Brings the characters' voices to the story.

Text. Complementary with other media, it can be used to depict background, complex processes, and big ideas.

Graphics. It can take you where cameras can't go. A great way to describe processes that explain how something works.

Today, there are also storytelling materials on the websites of Uzbekistan. In particular, we can see good examples of storytelling in the example of the gazeta.uz. On October 11, 2022, the storytelling entitled “Toshkent ramzlariga chizgilar: “Chorsu”dagi ovqat bozori” [9] (“Drawings of Tashkent symbols: the food market in Chorsu”) was published. In it, the story begins with the image of the food market located in the “Chorsu” market in Tashkent, so that the reader's imagination captures the image of that environment and appearance. The journalist also included the stories of chefs who have been working in the food market for many years, which created the basis for more interesting material. Storytelling is enriched with a general picture of the market, portraits of chefs, pictures of the market taken from different angles, and it allows you to read the story imaginatively.

In addition, gazeta.uz covered another story titled “Odamlarimiz hayotini obinsonsiz tasavvur qilib bo’lmaydi” [10] (“The life of our people cannot be imagined without bread” in an interesting way. It contains stories about bread, stories of bakers, text about work processes and many process pictures. In the lead part of storytelling, “Novvoylar — tandirchilar qanday yashashadi va ishlashadi?” (“Bakers how live and work?”) the question can be answered in detail through the story.

Looking at these storytellings, we can understand that if the story consisted of just text, it would probably be very boring for the reader. Due to the lack of multimedia, it could not be read to the end. However, the pictures, graphics, and audio in the storytelling made the text more readable. In fact, this is the task of storytelling. It is to present long texts to the audience in an interesting way, using the elements of multimedia effectively.

Multimedia stories are fun challenges for your students and empower them to share their ideas and concerns with the wider world. There are several possibilities for creating storytelling on the Internet. A journalist can use different platforms, depending on the preparation of storytelling in narrative, animation, text format. For example, we can cite sites such as Store, Niche, NtoryLab, Unfold to create mini storytelling in the form of a story. They have various unusual designs and templates. Platforms such as Hype Text, Legend, AppForType will help to create examples of storytelling in text format. Animated storytelling is created on sites such as Zoetroptic, Mojoo Art, Mojo, Adobe Spark Post. Storytelling has a wide range of opportunities to influence the audience, and it is not difficult to make them interactive through various sites on the Internet.

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